

Non-Invasive Modes of Somatic Therapy In Individuals Who Intellectualise Their Feelings

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Since the growing popularity of Psychology in mainstream culture, there's been a growing trend of people trying to "go to therapy", or therapising themselves. There is more information now than ever on how to analyse your own thoughts, behaviours and emotions. This has created a sphere of people who are too self aware; people who know what thought processes underlie their maladaptive behaviours as well as what can fix them.

Despite knowing their emotions and feelings, they are unable to change their behaviours for some unknown reason.

The ones who do go on to be able to change these behaviours, they seem to feel that their actions don't align with who they are, rendering them unable to cope mentally, that is to say, internally. These are the people who intellectualise their feelings.

There also has been a growing trend now in mainstream internet culture, talking about the risks of intellectualising your emotions which stems from these people who still struggle despite having done the internal mental work here, introduced the concept of "feeling your emotions instead of intellectualising them."

This has led to figuring out maladaptive thought patterns. This has, in this internet space debate among people about what exactly that means, and multiple people online trying to explain how they should feel their emotions in their body and not their mind, again using very vague language and word usage.

What seems to stump people is that these people telling them to "feel" their emotions don't account for the fact that the word 'feeling' has come to mean 'thinking'. This is again, due to the ever growing popularity of CBT and the popular belief that your feelings and emotions are being controlled by your thoughts. So, in the minds of these people who are stumped, they can't figure out that they are not supposed to think about their anger, sadness, happiness, shame, joy, fear, but rather actually somatically feel them in their bodies. So far, they have been employing non-somatic methods of therapy on themselves.

Essentially, the claim is that these people who intellectualise their feelings actually need somatic modes of therapy. This led me to think about why somatic therapies work better on people with past trauma, and why it would work better on this group of people specifically, as well. For this purpose, I have taken to the basic biological sciences as a theoretical framework to understand this better.

The Nervous System™ and The Lymphatic System™ is the thing that will help with Somatic Processing in these individuals.

I was 14 when I was first diagnosed with PCOS. I wasn't sure what it was in the first place. They explained that it was basically cysts in my ovaries that caused irregular periods, which I have had for almost 4.5 years. They give me a list of food items to avoid if I had PCOS,

which was rice, wheat, and basically all forms of carbs. My mom obviously was like, that's bs being the indian mom that she is, she was like, you're going to eat rice and roti like normal and well, being 14, I didn't exactly have control over my diet, so I had a "fuck it" attitude and gorged on all possible carbs. I have this black and white thinking, either I quit it, or I don't. My brother was in support of me, "but if it's the science that says it, then she's not wrong." My mom dismissed it anyways. I started looking up things about PCOS, whatever the google search results would give me, I talked about it with my sister, and my sister asked me to try yoga. So I looked up yoga on google and its benefits, I found a lot of eat these things and don't eat these other things, with no scientific proof, and found a lot of what i at the time thought was bs. I did however, find the science for Yoga and the general no carbs advice, which is also correct, but later I realised it was a very clinical approach. Those videos at the time did not highlight anything about why certain sugars were good, and the studies that I'd started to see only asked to avoid Sugar as a whole. Later I started doing more research about that and types of sugars, because I found out that inositol is a type of sugar. Though I did not actually do any proper research until COVID.

So, back to the yoga thing, I started seeing that it may help with calming down anxiety and stuff, and since my sister was studying Psychology, I thought, "okay, let me try this" because she said that the obesity could be result of anxiety and depression and yoga helps with those and anxiety and depression does correlate with obesity a lot.

So I started doing yoga, it was a little difficult with my brother creeping on me and my mom basically enabling it, but, I tried. Then, it started getting worse, my brother and mom are a bad combination to be around, they were the classic narcissists, like NPD level. I found that on reddit on r/raisedbynarcissists and then started doing research on Narcissists. The stuff on reddit taught me about gaslighting, different methods of manipulation, how there's golden childs, the black sheep, the enablers, in a family dynamic and most of them were Asian kids talking about how it was ingrained in their cultures, like me, basically. All the resources though were American literature, and mostly talking about Domestic and Partner abuse from Narcissists. Finally, I became so suicidal that I could not get out of bed and eventually, thankfully, my school asked my mom to take me to a psychiatrist or psychologist. My mother then asked me if I wanted to go, and I was finally relieved that I would finally get the help I needed. Then I saw a psychiatrist, which was amazing, but the psychiatrist wasn't. It's not like I could talk about my mom or my brother badly in an army hospital, I have no clue what they would have done, because I didn't want people to know my business, because everyone would have known and would have taken pity on me and it would have gotten worse. I know how mental health facilities are, and I imagined that it would be even worse in India. He kept chalking my depression up to the fact that I was fat, and despite me saying that it wasn't he kept saying, like a broken record, "Are you sure it's not because you're fat?" and I obviously looked upset, so he said "You look upset that I called you fat", and I wanted to tell him, "I am upset that you think that only because I'm fat." but I didn't. I knew what my problems were, I just didn't want to tell him because he said at the starting, "Oh, you're clearly not that depressed, you brushed your hair and wore clean clothes," and in my mind, I said, "because my mom forced me to and her image obviously depends on that, especially because I'm a girl, even more so," the fact that he didn't understand or think that, told me he was not the right psych. So, he kept saying, "I think you're depressed that I called you fat," and he repeated that question at least 10 times and not once did he ask whether it was my family, because Indians have amazing families. So, even after I tried to drop the subject of

me being fat, he kept cutting me off and telling me and asking me about me being fat, i obviously frowned at him and glared at him. That is when he literally said "Hmm," and he fucking took out a notebook and wrote something and that made me get even more angry. Then I realised, "Oh, this guy is not it. Don't tell him anything, he'll make your life worse." and that was confirmed when he then later wanted to talk to my mother alone. She would have beaten the shit out of me if she found out that i said anything about our family issues. I am so glad I didn't. Eventually, I met the school counsellor, and they talked to me, and asked me whether I would like to come to class or be "homeschooled" and I told them I would rather be homeschooled, and then they gave me information about NIOS and talked to my mother. Then I dropped out of the school I was in, then since my mom needed to be posted somewhere else too, they decided that I could live with my sister and i moved in with her. That was truly freeing. I moved in with my sister at 16. So, I signed up for NIOS Secondary School. I loved that I could choose my subjects. I took English, Science, Psychology, Home Science, Economics. So I ended up just doing chores. Learning how to brush my teeth and bathe myself daily on time, in a schedule, as well as do my morning exercise because I would literally forget. I literally could not keep track of time. My sister would remind me, "Did you brush your teeth?" "Did you do your yoga?" "Did you eat breakfast?" "Did you shower?" and I'd realise, "Oh, no. I forgot." Then I'd get to doing that. Then I slowly started opening up to my sister and then we started talking about how horrible mom was and bonded over it, and she told me that "There's a reason why I begged to go to boarding school, and I would rather have gone to this particular boarding school than deal with mom," and she said how my mom had lied to her and used to call her and tell her that I am a liar and that I lie all the time, I never lied. I only started lying after a certain point, because I realised that there was no point in telling her the truth, so I just started lying about everything, then it did start bleeding into the rest of my life too.

I got much better, started learning more about Psychology. Then I realised that I was an insomniac when I was 13-14, and I used to think that if you are insomniac, it means that you don't get even a wink of sleep, then I saw that you can be considered insomniac if you sleep for about 3-4 hours a day too, according to the DSM manuals. I slept for 20-40 minutes per day, had visual hallucinations because of it, both during class and daytime. Then I started realising that I also was dissociating, having derealistical episodes and having panic attacks as well as anxiety attacks. I had anxiety attacks literally 24/7, I'm not exaggerating, and in between, as a little treat, I would have panic attacks. I would also be dissociating 24/7, and having derealisation and depersonalisation thingies as another little treat.

I also realised that I coped with it by daydreaming, and there was a specific symptom that I saw, which was "maladaptive daydreaming", because I would walk around and talk to myself and pretend I am some character in some anime or film or game or fanfiction or something or the other.

I also had this time blindness and bad attention span and bad short term memory, but I also knew that I had really good memory for things that I cared about. I presented with typical ADHD symptoms, as well as Autism symptoms as well as Schizophrenic symptoms with delusions of grandeur, paranoia, psychosis and hallucinations.

I have had auditory hallucinations since I was a child, and was delusional since I was a child, even before the trauma had happened. Then, I started having somatic hallucinations after my brother started abusing me when I was 5, actually, I just realised that those somatic

hallucinations are from when I was 3-4 years old when my brother would take me to those maids' houses and they would molest us. From knowing what has happened to my brother, or knowing what was happening from my sister's memories, it seems like he was also being molested from a young age. Apparently, the nannies used to lock my sister in the house and take him away for hours on end when my mom was at work. Knowing this, I did feel some sort of empathy for him, but, after you turn 25, there's honestly no excuse.

I was able to put 2 and 2 together and figured that since he was a male, his way of lashing out was to sexually assault someone else, because that was his normal. Usually, males tend to externalise their mental illnesses in the form of aggression towards others and females have a tendency to internalise that towards themselves, that is the way they are raised in society.

I have always been interested in these things, so I saw studies, made my own conclusions, etc. I remember the studies talking about how men and women are inherently different simply because of their career choices, and people in favour of this would talk about this study that was done on toddlers seeing what types of toys they pick up, and using that to say that females pick up toys with faces, dolls, kitchen stuff, etc and males pick up trucks, cars, guns, etc and said, because "males are more technical and females are more feelings oriented" which was bs because that study was done on 3 year olds, and there have been many scientific studies on how babies, newborns literally absorb information since the day they are born. 3 years is too old. The kind of families that they come from, they know better than to stray away from their roles. Humans are adaptable, and this is where I brought in my own theory of evolution, I call it "Social Evolution", so to just chalk it up to biology is just wrong, because your environment affects biology and vice versa, they are not two separate things. I knew this because of Psychology and how I know that with PCOS, I am feeling anxious and depressed because my neurotransmitters/hormones are not regulated a certain way. That happened because of my environment in the first place. Because my environment controls my biological processes, you can't say that my biology controls my social self. It is the social conditioning that really controls your biological processes.

To elaborate, I will bring in the concept of genetics and epigenetics with two basic example. Genetics, is well, your genes, what you're born with, your DNA, RNA, mRNA, etc etc, there's different specific terms for the specific thingies, I will not go in depth yet. It's basically how you inherit skin colour, eye colour, facial features, body types, hair colour, hair type, etc.

Epigenetics deals with how your genes get expressed due to the environment, and your parents' choices, etc and how they evolved. If you understand evolutionary theory, you will know that you biologically adapt over generations to either climate, terrain, agricultural stuff, etc, but it goes deeper than that.

For example, 1. Smoking addiction in a parent VS the same addiction in their child.
2. Lactose Intolerance in Vietnamese people during the time period of the war (which war?), their access to dairy was taken away (?), so their progeny (either devolved or never had any?) didn't have the enzymes to digest Lactase. This happens because the body would need more energy to code production of these lactase enzymes, and if the environment does not call for digesting lactase, there is no need for the body to have these enzymes. the

body needs to save energy and prime it for survival, according to evolutionary theory.

So essentially, evolutionary theory provides a reason for the biological processes happening, and the reason is supposed to be survival of the most efficient.

Now I started exploring genes because of Psychology and Neuroscience in the first place to cure my PCOS and mental health issues. We've just delved into the evolutionary science of adaptation, which takes energy and the body will always choose the more efficient path, conserving energy.

The reason I started delving into these gene theories is because I wanted to find out why I specifically evolved to have PCOS as a defense mechanism and why others did not. For this, I need to explain how PCOS works and the evolutionary reasons for it, as well as why it expresses itself in the kind of symptoms it does.

So, PCOS is Poly-Cystic Ovarian Syndrome, is basically, as the name describes is when you have multiple cysts in your ovaries. But, this is not the main marker for PCOS. It is a result of all these other things that are happening wrong with your body, specifically your endocrine system. They are divided into two types, Insulin Resistant (IR) type and Non-Insulin Resistant Type (??), what I am going to be talking about is IR PCOS.

Basically, if you have IR PCOS, you are considered pre-diabetic. With IR PCOS, if your predecessors have any sort of Diabetes or Blood Sugar issues, you are more susceptible to have this kind of PCOS. Which checks out. If you are a female child born after a male child, because the mother has more androgens in her system, you are even more susceptible to IR PCOS. This also checks out.

I will talk more about the symptoms and issues that come with PCOS. The first few are Obesity, Hirsutism, Acanthosis Nigricans, Anxiety and Depression. These are the noticeable symptoms. Now I will talk about the causes of these symptoms:

1. **Anxiety** and Depression - there's more going on here, but this causes excess Cortisol to be released and Adrenaline also
2. **Hirsutism** - excess Cortisol and Adrenaline production causes Androgens to be released, which causes Hirsutism
3. **Acanthosis Nigricans** - This Adrenal and Renal gland release causes a malfunction in the Pancreas, ie, the gland that releases Insulin
4. **Obesity** - Then due to an excess of Insulin release, ie, Hyperinsulinemia, it causes Hyperglycemia.
5. Due to the Hyperglycemia, it releases more insulin, basically how Type 2 Diabetes would work, and you can become fully diabetic also if you don't get this under control

How it causes excess sugar in your blood is due to the hunger hormones being messed up by the pancreas ? which is regulated by the insulin.

So, the hunger hormones are Leptin, Ghrelin, etc. One tells you when you feel satiated, another tells you when you are hungry, so on and so forth. These are controlled by the sugar in your blood, the blood sugar crashes and lows sort of control this whole process, I won't get too in depth into this. But I will get a little in depth into the Endocrine system:

which is obviously controlled by the **Pituitary Gland, ie the Brain and nervous system**, which is in turn controlled by the Lymphatic System.

The Brain Stem (Subconscious, Dreams, etc.),

How the Vagus Nerve connects to the Thymus.

Thymus development in a person.

The Lymph system in brief, relate the Thymus to Psychological Trauma plus Vagus Nerve, and

How the Vagus Nerve healing happens with the Thymus healing and why,

I HAVE GOT IMPORTANT THINGS TO TELL YOU!!! ABOUT CHILDHOOD
TRAUMA AND CHRONIC ILLNESSES

**!!What I say may not be a 100% true so
do your own research and believe me
at your own discretion. !!**

**Okay, so I've been doing research about the thymus. There's a
few things:**

- It is an organ of the **lymphatic system**. The stuff that controls your immune system.
- It is ALSO an organ of the **endocrine system**.
- Basically, it's part of both systems.
- The endocrine system acts on the changes in the neurotransmitters in the brain, and controls the hormones
- It connects to the Brain Stem **AND THE NERVOUS SYSTEM**
- The Thymus connects to the **nervous system** through the **VAGUS NERVE**.

Here are the functions of the Thymus:

1. As part of the **lymphatic system**, it obviously creates T cells and stuff.
2. As a part of the **endocrine system**, it secretes hormones that help in developing the lymphatic system.
 - (eg- thymosin, thymopoetin, thymulin)
 - The Endocrine System controls functions that depend on cortisol, the "stress hormone"
 - ie, anything to do with hormones in your body, like —
 - thyroxine from the thyroid; adrenaline from the adrenals; testosterone, estrogen, and progesterone from the testes and ovaries; and so on
 - **Another thing it does is PRODUCE OXYTOCIN, as part of the endocrine system**
 - Oxytocin is secreted by The gonads (ovaries or testes), The Pituitary Gland (in the brain) and The Thymus.
 - (Most hormones are just called neurotransmitters when they work with the **nervous system** instead of the endocrine system, like adrenaline is just literally epinephrine, they're the same thing, except one is a hormone and the other is a neurotransmitter)
 - So any hormone is also a neurotransmitter
1. ***The other interesting thing it does, one of the main things is help in the maturation of the immune system. It is the most active during childhood and adolescence.***
 - So by the time you've grown up, the lymph tissue that makes up the thymus has turned into fat tissue and is mostly useless as an adult.
 - The oxytocin helps in the maturation of the lymphatic system.

Do you know what Oxytocin does?

- You must have heard of it. The "love hormone/neurotransmitter"
- It is associated with trust, empathy, social interaction and such in humans and other animals
- It also acts as an Anti-inflammatory, Anti-Oxidant substance physically in lymphatic tissue

- Cortisol and Oxytocin work together to get you many endocrine responses, such as anxiety when you have intense trauma and trust issues, etc
- Cortisol is driven by environmental stress, hence its colloquial name, the "stress hormone"
- Cortisol controls how the rest of the endocrine system works
- So, cortisol and oxytocin make up most of your endocrine system's responses.
- The brain decides whether to produce cortisol or not based on the amount of oxytocin it releases
- If you have imbalanced oxytocin levels, it propagates the imbalance of cortisol

The result of this is that another neat thing the thymus does is regulate your nervous system through all of these processes.

You remember how the thymus is connected to the Vagus Nerve, the thing you hear about all over tiktok?

- The Vagus nerve is one of the **12 Cranial Nerves™**
- The cranial nerves are involved in processing sensory information and other information from the motor nerves
- They then control the **involuntary** bodily responses that result from this, ie, they are part of the **parasympathetic nervous system**.
- These responses include stuff like processing visual information, tasting food, swallowing food, raising your heartbeat or slowing it down, increasing the temperature in your body, making your stomach rumble when you're hungry, etc
- **Some of them are involved in the voluntary movements/sympathetic nervous system too**, but what I mean is that they process the data you get automatically despite some of these using functions of the voluntary nervous system.
- Like, you can move your facial muscles to emote, move your tongue to speak, open and close your eyes because of these Cranial Nerves

- **BASICALLY, *the physical sensations that you feel as a result of any kind of stimulus, whether external or internal, is because of these cranial nerves.***
- I'm going to make an educated guess and say that the hormones and neurotransmitters in the body send signals to and from these cranial nerves to do all this, you can use the explanations I had about the thymus for this.

The Vagus Nerve is the 10th Cranial Nerve, labelled as "CN X"

- The Vagus Nerve is also the main nerve of the parasympathetic nervous system
- It specifically controls many automatic body processes. Stuff like controlling digestion, heart rate, breathing, saliva production, mood, and more
- Mood? Mood, you say? Yes, your mood. Because it is connected to the brain, the lymphatic system and the endocrine system through the Thymus.
- **The Thymus is not just connected to the Vagus Nerve, it's also connected to other Cranial Nerves**

You can probably see where I'm going with this, if not, well:

- The thymus regulates your nervous system.
- The thymus develops and is most active during childhood and adolescence
- Have you heard about the research that says that the ability to self soothe, or self regulate only develops by the time you're 6-7 years old?
- Babies can't self soothe or regulate their nervous system because their thymus is still developing.
- The thymus is connected to any trauma in your childhood
- This is also why childhood trauma is directly correlated to chronic illnesses in adulthood.

Your lymphatic system, your endocrine system and digestive system are the most affected somatically by childhood trauma

So if you have had childhood trauma, or you can't remember your childhood, it is possible you may have been diagnosed for some disorder(s) afflicting these systems:

1. Endocrine Disorders:

- I don't recall who it was, but there was this doctor who was determined to study obesity and took in a lot of obese patients to make them healthy again.
- He couldn't understand why certain things didn't work for obese patients that worked with other healthy patients
- His whole life was dedicated to studying metabolic disorders, ie, endocrine disorders
- You know what he found?
- All of his patients were afflicted with psychological childhood trauma, usually sexual trauma
- Examples: PCOS, Diabetes, Adrenal Fatigue, Hyperthyroidism, Hypothyroidism, Cushing's Disease, Hashimoto's Disease, Graves' Disease, etc,
- anything that can mess with your blood sugar levels and insulin levels, usually gives you intense fatigue, depression and anxiety, basically

1. Lymphatic Disorders

- The lymphatic system can be inflamed and cause intense brain fog because you have lymph nodes all over your body, especially many tiny vessels in your skull area, in an around the brain
- The lymphatic system is your immune system, phlegm is basically lymph fluid, so when your body is fighting off disease, you can't think at all, and you feel a pressure in your head, sinuses, etc
- This can result in a brain fog in the long run
- Examples: Graves' Disease, Cushing's Disease, Hashimoto's Disease, Lupus, Coeliac Disease, other autoimmune diseases, etc
- Any disease that affects your immune system/lymphatic system basically

1. Digestive Disorders:

- Bad Gut Flora as a result of emotional eating, again, due to trauma. Certain foods help and promote growth of the nice gut flora by providing a nice

micro-biome and other types of food create a hostile environment for the good gut flora, and a good habitat for the harmful ones

- this can result in your body not being able to digest certain things without complications, you may develop allergies to certain foods, your intestines and stomach in general are not as healthy
- Eating too much or too little of certain foods and foods in general can fuck up your stomach
- Examples: Gall Stones, IBS, GERD, Dairy Intolerance, Gluten Intolerance, etc

Some of these disorders overlap, that's because the functions in your body are shared by organs and overlap with each other.

If any of these issues are a result of psychological trauma, it's best if you concentrate on taking care of your thymus:

1. Eating healthy and working out will help your lymphatic/immune system.

2. Maybe going to someone who deals with somatic therapy or learning ways online, like stuff like Exercise, Stretching and Yoga, can help your nervous system learn to self-soothe and regulate itself.

3. Letting out your emotions in a healthy way can be done by (STEP 4 IS MOST IMPORTANT and MUST TAKE PRECEDENCE OVER ALL):

- **STEP 1: Pick your desired medium:** stationery-pens, pencils, colours, paints, paper, chart paper, glue, clay, your body-hands, legs, mouth, tongue, teeth, clothes, fabric, scissors, knives, box cutters, cardboard, boxing gloves, yoga mat, weights, fidget spinner, Rubik's shapes, whatever it is that makes you relax, literally whatever idk
- **STEP 2: Make sure you are in a safe space, where you can use your desired materials.** Wherever you can find it, maybe in your room, maybe in a park, maybe in a library (but you can't make sounds in a library so ymmv), maybe in the parking lot, school, the terrace of your building, idk pick one. Just make sure you can use your desired materials.
- **STEP 3: Trigger your trauma.** Start slow if you want to, just until you feel uncomfortable or start to feel nauseous. OR trigger the hell out of it. Think about it until you have a meltdown.
- **STEP 4: MAKE SURE THAT WHATEVER YOU DO, YOU ABSOLUTELY DO NOT HURT YOURSELF PHYSICALLY, LIKE AT ALL, DURING THE ENTIRETY OF THE WHOLE PROCESS.**
- **STEP 5: Introspection.** Keep thinking about your trauma. Use your materials, and do whatever makes you feel good. Remember the trauma.
- **STEP 6: Profit.** Do not break the rules of **STEP 4** no matter what. Repeat STEPS 4-5 as long as it takes. No, I will not elaborate any further.

You may feel some release after 3. and may find that you feel less stressed and even less triggered by your trauma than before. If not, reread and interpret the text again and try again.

Only if you want to, of course.

*Peter A. Levine, Eugene Gendlin, Carl Rogers, Jacob Francone Lussow, Isaac Asimov
("Man, The Unknown")*